

Preparation and Characterisation of Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Transition Metals. Part-IV. Amine Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Iron(II) Anthranilates

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Some octahedral complexes of cobalt(II) and iron(II) anthranilates with amines have been prepared and characterised. The complexes possess the following formulas on the basis of analysis and molar conductance, $[M(C_7H_5O_2N)_2(am)]_n$, $[M(C_7H_5O_2N)_2(dam)]_n$, where $M=Co$ or Fe , $am=$ ammonia or aniline, and $dam=$ ethylene diamine (en) or propylene diamine (pn), $[Co(Phen \text{ or } dipy)_2(C_7H_5O_2N)_2]$; $[M(dien)_2(C_7H_5O_2N)_2]$ and $[M(trien)(H_2O)_2(C_7H_5O_2N)_2]$, where $M=Co$ or Fe , $Phen=$ *o*-phenanthroline, $dipy=$ 2,2'-dipyridyl, $dien=$ diethylenetriamine and $trien=$ triethylenetetramine. The geometry of the complexes has been assigned on the basis of magnetic and electronic spectral data. The differences in the mode of coordination of the anthranilate ion as well as the different spin behaviour of iron(II) complexes has been explained on the basis of the base strength of the amines used.

DURING our studies on a series of mixed ligand complexes of transition metals derived from organic anions, a large number of complexes containing oxalate, succinate, phthalate, phthalimide and succinimide ions were prepared¹⁻⁵. In the present paper, we wish to report the complexes of cobalt(II) and iron(II) anthranilates with various amines as ammonia, aniline, ethylenediamine, propylenediamine, *o*-phenanthroline, 2,2'-dipyridyl, diethylenetriamine and triethylenetetramine. The complexes have been characterised on the basis of analysis, molar conductance, magnetic, and infrared and electronic spectral data. An attempt has been made to explain the different modes of coordination of anthranilate ions, in terms of increasing base strength of ligands.

Experimental

Preparation of cobalt(II) and iron(II) anthranilates: Calculated amount of anthranilic acid was suspended in water and treated with solid sodium bicarbonate till neutral. An aqueous solution of Co^{II} or Fe^{II} sulphate was added and the precipitate so obtained was filtered, dried and analysed. The analytical data are given in Table 1.

Preparation of complexes: A known weight of starting material was suspended in methanol and treated with the required amine in a little excess. The tri and tetramines were, however, added dropwise in the form of their methanolic solutions.

The solution was refluxed for 5-6 h. The resulting solution was concentrated and then subjected to crystallisation using petroleum ether and diethyl ether mixture. The complexes were dried and analysed and the data are given in the Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The proposed formulas of the various complexes are given in Table 1 and these suggest that in the complexes of ammonia, aniline, ethylenediamine or propylenediamine, the anthranilate ion is coordinated, acting as bidentate in the former and as monodentate in the latter case. However, in the tri and tetramine complexes of both the metals, the ion is not coordinated. The gradual decrease in the denticity of the ion is an outcome of the increased base strength of amines.

The ion has two possible sites of coordination, the NH_2 and $COOH$ groups, both of which are involved in coordination when weaker ligands, such as ammonia and aniline are used. If, however, the diamines are used, which are stronger than the former, only one coordinating site of the ion (COO^-) is used and is, therefore, monodentate in this case. But the complexes of both are non-electrolyte, because the ion is coordinated. On the other hand, when tri and tetramines are used which are very strong ligands, the anthranilate ion is prevented totally from the coordination and hence, these complexes are electrolytes. Conclusive

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC DATA

Sl. no.	Complex	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Λ (in nitrobenzene) Ω^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.
			Metal	C	H	N		
1.	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Pink	15.02 (15.23)	43.02 (43.66)	4.21 (4.71)	6.80 (7.28)	—	—
2.	$\text{Fe}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Dirty green	16.52 (16.81)	50.25 (50.62)	4.36 (4.85)	8.50 (8.44)	—	—
3.	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Steel grey	16.50 (16.13)	46.85 (46.03)	5.28 (4.96)	14.8 (15.34)	9.2	5.20
4.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2)_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Pink	11.65 (11.39)	61.08 (60.34)	5.61 (5.06)	11.2 (10.83)	8.5	4.98
5.	$[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Chocolate brown	19.60 (19.05)	47.21 (47.83)	5.90 (6.25)	18.02 (18.62)	9.0	5.43
6.	$[\text{Co}(\text{pn})_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Brown	12.60 (12.29)	51.20 (50.00)	6.15 (6.72)	17.02 (17.53)	8.8	5.18
7.	$[\text{Co}(\text{dien})_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Brownish black	11.2 (10.96)	49.0 (49.15)	7.21 (7.12)	20.61 (20.85)	25.60	5.02
8.	$[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Brown	12.10 (11.47)	47.51 (46.78)	7.08 (6.67)	16.92 (16.36)	24.28	4.89
9.	$[\text{Co}(\text{phen})_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Dark green	8.80 (8.52)	66.50 (65.99)	4.62 (4.08)	12.60 (12.15)	8.7	5.28
10.	$[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Dark green	9.50 (9.15)	63.20 (63.45)	4.20 (4.38)	13.64 (13.06)	8.7	5.30
11.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2]$	Reddish green	15.6 (15.42)	46.81 (46.42)	5.00 (5.01)	15.50 (15.47)	8.8	5.89
12.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{en})_2]$	Red	12.6 (12.46)	48.91 (48.23)	6.92 (6.29)	18.80 (18.75)	8.2	5.98
13.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{pn})_2]$	Reddish brown	12.00 (11.72)	51.06 (50.42)	6.80 (6.77)	17.53 (17.64)	8.6	5.82
14.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{dien})_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Almond colour	10.61 (10.45)	49.96 (49.43)	7.10 (7.16)	21.0 (20.97)	27.15	0.68
15.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{trien})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2]$	Dark red	11.20 (10.94)	46.78 (47.06)	6.90 (6.71)	16.51 (16.47)	22.60	0.72

evidence for this behaviour is obtained from the infrared spectra as discussed.

In the complexes of ammonia, aniline, ethylene and propylene diamine ν_{NH} appears in the form of a sharp doublet at 3200 cm^{-1} indicating that NH_2 group of the amines is coordinated. The ν_{NH} in free anthranilate ion occurs at 3350 cm^{-1} . The same merges with the ν_{NH} of ammonia and aniline, showing that this group is also involved in coordination. In case of diamine complexes, the formulas show that the ion is only monodentate in nature and in accordance a very strong band is observed at 3360 cm^{-1} which becomes distinctly visible in the *o*-phenanthroline and 2,2'-dipyridyl complexes (which are tertiary amines) at 390 cm^{-1} and supports the statement that NH_2 group of anthranilate ion is not coordinated to metal(II) in these complexes. The similar situation exists in case of tri and tetramines too, where the ν_{NH} of coordinated amine and of free anthranilate ion are seen^{6,7} at 3200 and 3350 cm^{-1} .

The asymmetric stretch due to carboxylate ion occurs in sodium anthranilate at 1525 cm^{-1} . The same band is observed at $1400 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes of ammonia, aniline and diamines, while at $1520 \pm 20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes of tri and tetramines. It is reported that coordination as well as esterification of carboxylate ion causes large negative shifts in its position^{8,9}. It is thus concluded that COO^- ion is coordinated in the former and is free in the

latter complexes. These observations thus confirm the different dentities of the ion.

All the complexes of cobalt(II), and ammonia, ethylene diamine or propylene diamine complexes of iron(II) are paramagnetic corresponding to spin-free octahedral configuration while diethylenetriamine and triethylenetetramine complexes of iron(II) anthranilate are spin-paired. The octahedral geometry is confirmed by the electronic spectral data as follows.

Cobalt(II) complexes: These complexes exhibit the characteristic bands corresponding to the spin-allowed ligand field transitions of octahedral geometry at 21.50 and 8.50 kK designated as V_3 and V_1 , respectively. The V_3 band being of very weak intensity is not clearly visible while V_2 is invariably broken down in two components. The Dq and β values are around 825 and 1010 cm^{-1} , supporting the octahedral structure¹⁰⁻¹². The Dq values increase in the order, ammonia, diamine, tri- or tetramine as expected.

Iron complexes: The three iron complexes (nos. 11, 12, 13) exhibit only one band corresponding to ${}^5E_g \rightarrow {}^5T_{2g}$ transition, which is equal to Dq . The same thus lies around 900 cm^{-1} . The spectra of the spin-paired complexes (nos. 14, 15) are very complicated, in which the definite assignment of the bands is difficult. However, only one band corresponding to the main spin-allowed transition is seen at 14.00 kK. The Dq values are around

1400 cm^{-1} which are sufficiently high to induce spin-pairing in these complexes¹³⁻¹⁵.

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